

PERFORMANCE OF PMFBY (PRADHAN MANTRI FASAL BIMA YOJANA) IN PARBHANI DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA STATE

V. G. Murmure *, R. D. Shelke **, S. H. Kamble ***, P. A. Bhosale ****, P. K. Thakare *****

*PG Scholar (Agri), Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India.

murmurevarsha@gmail.com

** Associate Professor (Agricultural Economics), Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India.

*** Associate Professor (Agricultural Economics), Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India.

**** PG Scholar (Agri), Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India.

***** PG Scholar (Agri), Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India.

MS Received: 10.09.2024; MS Revised:08.10.2024; MS Accepted:09.10.2024

MS 3309

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS)

Abstract

Present study was conducted to investigate the progress and performance of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in Parbhani district of Maharashtra state, focusing on the talukas of Gangakhed, Jintur, Parbhani, and Selu. The farmers of Parbhani district were facing the problems of heavy rainfall, crop diseases and droughts over a period of several time, they were losing income from their farming activities. Primary data were collected from 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers during the 2023 kharif and rabi season, and secondary data from relevant publications. Using analytical techniques, Descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation, and the coefficient of variation, and Garrett's Ranking Technique. The data shows steady growth in insurance participation and payouts, particularly in kharif, though rabi season faces challenges in benefits and payouts. Compensation mechanisms improve income stability by reducing variability. Key constraints include delays in claims, insufficient compensation, and lack of crop awareness, requiring better efficiency and communication. Farmers suggest faster claims, expanded coverage for small farmers, improved local support, and greater transparency to enhance the scheme's effectiveness. This paper would throw light on the positive performance of PMFBY in Parbhani district.

Keywords: Crop insurance, PMFBY, Growth rate, Income stability, Constraints, Suggestions

Introduction

Agriculture is vital to India's economy, supporting most of the (70%) of the population and significantly contributing to national income. Crop insurance is essential for ensuring farmers' financial stability by protecting them from risks like natural disasters, pests, and market fluctuations. This security promotes the adoption of modern farming practices, leading to improved agricultural productivity and overall economic growth. Crop insurance increases crop losses over both space and time, provides farmers social security, gives them the ability to help individuals, helps them conserve their worth and promotes major spending in agriculture to increase yield and boost agricultural output.

In India, crop insurance has developed significantly to include risks associated with agriculture, especially those due to pest infestations and climate variability. Initial attempts, such as the 1972–1973 pilot programs, experimented with "individual" and "area approach" insurance models. The first nationwide initiative, the Comprehensive Crop Insurance Scheme (CCIS), was launched in 1985 in tandem with the Seventh Five-Year Plan, implementing Professor Dandekar's suggestions. In 1999, the National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (NAIS) replaced its place, and with it more coverage. The Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) was introduced in 2016 to offer more comprehensive and effective crop insurance, replacing all previous plans.

The Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY), launched in 2016, is one of the world's largest crop insurance programs, aimed at providing risk protection to Indian farmers. It offers subsidized premiums, with farmers paying only 2 per cent for *kharif* crops, 1.5 per cent for *rabi* crops, and up to 5 per cent for annual commercial crops, while the central and state governments share the remaining premium cost. PMFBY merged and improved upon previous crop insurance schemes to offer financial support in case of crop failure, stabilize farmers' incomes, encourage credit flow, and promote the adoption of modern agricultural practices.

The present study evaluated the effectiveness of PMFBY in Parbhani district, Maharashtra, an area known for its distinct climatic and socio-economic conditions. Parbhani serves as a valuable case study for understanding how PMFBY performs in a region where farmers face unique agricultural challenges. With 2,85,610 total farmers over an area of 524.27 thousand hectares during the *kharif* season, and a total insured value of Rs. 2 77 371.06 lakh, this district offers significant insights into the strengths and weaknesses of PMFBY. The study

examines key areas such as farmer awareness, ease of access, claim settlement processes, and the impact of the scheme on income stabilization. (Source: www.pmfby.gov.in)

The key barriers to adopting the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) are delays in claim payments and insufficient compensation. To enhance its effectiveness and increase farmer participation, policymakers should prioritize faster claims processing, broader coverage for small farmers, and the establishment of local administrative cells. Modernizing crop loss assessments, increasing indemnity amounts, and implementing transparent processes with grievance redressal mechanisms will ensure fair compensation and foster trust. These improvements will make PMFBY more equitable, efficient, and effective in protecting agricultural livelihoods.

Objectives

1. To study the progress of PMFBY in Parbhani district of Maharashtra state
2. To analyse the impact of PMFBY on income stability of farmers
3. To identify the weaknesses in implementation of PMFBY and suggest suitable measures for its improvement

Materials And Methods

This study analyses the progress of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in Parbhani district over 2016-17 to 2023-24, focusing on growth metrics including insured farmers, insured area, claims reported and approved, total claims paid, and beneficiaries. Growth was assessed using the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) formula:

The CAGR was estimated by using following formulas.

$$Y_1 = a.b^t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where,

Y = Dependent variable for which growth rate is to be estimated (Number of farmer insured / Area insured / Reported claim / Approved claim / Total claim paid / Total farmer benefitted)

t = Time variable

b = Regression coefficient

a = Intercept

This equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follows

$$\text{Log } y = \text{log } a + t \text{ Log } b \dots\dots(2)$$

Then the per cent compound growth rate (r) was computed using the equation.

$$\text{CGR } (r) = [\text{Antilog } (\text{log } b) - 1] \times 100 \dots(3)$$

The significance of the regression coefficient was tested using the student's 't' test

Descriptive statistics were used to analyse income, including mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation (CV), and Income Stability Index. The Income Stability Index was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Income stability index} = 1 - \text{CV}$$

indicating income stability for both insured and non-insured farmers. The CV and income stability index allowed for a comparative analysis of income variation and stability between the two groups i. e without compensation and with compensation.

For identifying implementation weaknesses, Garrett's Ranking Technique was applied. Farmers ranked various challenges, and the ranks were converted into scores using Garrett's Table.

These scores were then averaged to identify the most significant issues affecting PMFBY implementation in Parbhani district.

Results And Discussion

Progress of crop insurance schemes

The study revealed that the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) scheme, focusing on compound annual growth rate (CAGR). The year wise data on number of insured farmers, area insured, reported claim, approved claim, total claim paid and total farmer's benefit of *kharif* and *rabi* in Parbhani district for the last 8 years i.e., 2016 to 2023 have been collected from the www.pmfby.gov.in.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of insured farmers under PMFBY for to period 2016-17 to 2022-23

The analysis of Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for insured farmers across India, Maharashtra, and Parbhani, reveal that contrasting trends in agricultural insurance doption during the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons. Table 1. Shows that at the national level, India experienced a decline in insured farmers, with a negative CAGR of -7 per cent per annum in the *kharif* season and -2 per cent per annum in the *rabi* season, indicating challenges such as ineffective insurance schemes and low farmer awareness. Conversely, Maharashtra demonstrated significant growth, achieving a CAGR of 20 per cent per annum for *kharif* and 3 per cent per annum for *rabi*, likely due to effective state policies and targeted awareness programs. Parbhani district also showed consistent growth, with a 4 per cent per annum CAGR for both seasons, reflecting a steady increase in insurance uptake. Overall, these trends highlight the disparities in agricultural insurance adoption across regions and seasons, emphasizing the need for tailored approaches to enhance farmer participation.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of area of insured under PMFBY for to period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Table. 2 presented the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) and associated t-values for the area insured under crop insurance schemes from 2016 to 2023 across India, Maharashtra, and Parbhani during the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons. At the national level, India demonstrated minimal growth in the insured area, with a CAGR of 1 per cent per annum for both seasons, indicating a slow and cautious adoption of crop insurance. In contrast, Maharashtra showed robust growth, achieving a CAGR of 19 per cent per annum in the *kharif* season and 4 per cent per annum in the *rabi* season, suggesting a seasonal variation in insurance uptake, potentially due to the higher perceived risks associated with *kharif* crops. Parbhani exhibited moderate growth, with a 3 per cent per annum CAGR for *kharif* and a slightly higher 4 per cent per annum for *rabi*, reflecting ongoing efforts to enhance insurance coverage despite potential challenges like limited awareness and financial constraints. Overall, these trends highlight significant regional disparities in crop insurance adoption, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to boost participation.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of reported Claim under PMFBY for to period 2016-17 to 2022-23

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) and t-values for reported claims in crop insurance table. 3 shows that across India, Maharashtra, and Parbhani during the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons. At the national level, reported claims increased steadily with an 8 per cent per annum CAGR

in *kharif* and a significant 44 per cent per annum CAGR in *rabi*, indicating heightened risks for *rabi* crops potentially linked to adverse weather patterns or pest outbreaks. In Maharashtra, however, a negative CAGR of -41 per cent per annum in the *kharif* season suggests a notable decline in claims, possibly due to improved agricultural practices or issues within the insurance process, while claims remained stable with a 1 per cent per annum CAGR in *rabi*. Parbhani reported a marginal increase of 1 per cent per annum in *kharif* claims but a 13 per cent per annum CAGR during the *rabi* season, indicating growing vulnerabilities in *rabi* crops and possibly enhanced farmer awareness in reporting claims. These trends highlight varying regional responses to risks and the performance of crop insurance programs.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of approved Claim under PMFBY for to period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Data revealed in table. 4 the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of approved insurance claims for the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons across India, Maharashtra, and Parbhani. At the national level, there was a significant negative CAGR of -60 per cent per annum for approved claims in the *kharif* season, indicating severe declines in claim approval rates, possibly due to stricter criteria or processing inefficiencies. The *rabi* season also saw a notable decrease with a -26 per cent per annum CAGR. In Maharashtra, approved claims during *kharif* similarly declined by -42 per cent per annum, reflecting administrative challenges or policy changes, although *rabi* claims showed a modest recovery with a 3 per cent per annum growth rate. In contrast, Parbhani experienced positive growth in both seasons, with a 4 per cent CAGR for *kharif* and 5 per cent per annum for *rabi*, suggesting improved efficiency in the claims process and better support for farmers. These trends highlight significant disparities in claim approval rates across regions, underscoring the need for enhancements in insurance processing at the national and state levels.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of total claim paid under PMFBY for to period 2016-17 to 2022-23

The analysis of total claims paid, as outlined in the data, table.5 reveals mixed trends across India, Maharashtra, and Parbhani during the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons. At the national level, a negative CAGR of -5 per cent per annum for *kharif* and -20 per cent per annum for *rabi* indicates a decline in insurance payouts, possibly due to reduced claims frequency, severity, or coverage issues that hinder financial support for farmers. In contrast, Maharashtra experienced a positive CAGR of 7 per cent per annum for *kharif* claims, suggesting effective interventions or improved coverage, while *rabi* claims saw a decline of -13 per cent per annum, indicating challenges in providing adequate support during that season. Parbhani exhibited a strong positive CAGR of 15 per cent per annum, for *kharif* claims, reflecting increased payouts, but faced a -9 per cent per annum decline in *rabi* claims, pointing to potential inconsistencies in claims processing or coverage. Overall, these findings highlight significant regional disparities and the need for improvements in insurance systems to better support farmers during critical growing seasons.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of total farmer benefit under PMFBY for to period 2016-17 to 2022-23

The table.6 presented that the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of overall farmer benefits from insurance during the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons across India, Maharashtra, and Parbhani. At the national level, a -6 per cent per annum CAGR for *kharif* benefits and a -19 per cent per annum CAGR for *rabi* benefits indicate a significant decline in financial support for farmers, suggesting potential issues with claims volume or payout adequacy. In Maharashtra, total farmer benefits showed slight stability with a 1 per cent per annum CAGR in *kharif*, but a sharp -19 per cent per annum decline during the *rabi* season mirrors national trends, highlighting systemic challenges in providing adequate support. Conversely, Parbhani experienced a robust 12 per cent per annum CAGR in *kharif* benefits, indicating improved financial support for farmers, though *rabi* benefits fell by -12 per cent per annum, reflecting localized challenges in coverage effectiveness. These findings emphasize the disparities in insurance

efficacy across regions and seasons, underscoring the need for targeted improvements in insurance programs to enhance farmer support.

Impact of crop insurance schemes on income stability of farmers

The analysis of income stability between the "Without Compensation" and "With Compensation" groups table. 7 revealed that compensation mechanisms positively impacted income stability.

Standard Deviation

The standard deviation measures the dispersion or variability in income within each group. The "Without Compensation" group exhibits a higher standard deviation (14636.60) compared to the "With Compensation" group (13722.80). This suggests that incomes in the "Without Compensation" group was more dispersed and less consistent. In contrast, the "With Compensation" group demonstrates reduced variability, indicating that the income levels in this group was more clustered around the mean.

Mean

The mean income in the "With Compensation" group is 68352.20, which is higher than the mean income of the "Without Compensation" group, which was 67795.90. This suggests that, on average, individuals in the "With Compensation" group had a slightly higher income. This difference, although modest, could indicate that compensation mechanisms positively impact average income levels.

Coefficient of Variation (COV)

The COV is a normalized measure of the dispersion of the data, calculated as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean. The COV for the "Without Compensation" group was 0.22, while for the "With Compensation" group, it was 0.20. A lower COV in the "With Compensation" group indicates greater relative stability and less variability in income relative to the mean. This suggests that compensation mechanisms may contribute to more consistent income distribution within this group.

Income Stability Index

The Income Stability Index was higher for the "With Compensation" group (0.80) compared to the "Without Compensation" group (0.78). Although the difference was slight, it indicates that the "With Compensation" group enjoys a marginally more stable income. This index further supports the notion that compensation mechanisms contribute to reducing income volatility.

The comparative analysis between the "Without Compensation" and "With Compensation" groups demonstrates that compensation mechanisms have a positive impact on income stability. The "With Compensation" group exhibits lower income variability, a higher mean income, and a reduced coefficient of variation, all of which contribute to a more stable income profile as indicated by the Income Stability Index. These findings suggest that compensation mechanisms can play a crucial role in enhancing income stability, reducing income inequality, and promoting financial well-being. Policymakers and stakeholders should consider these benefits when designing income support programs and compensation structures to ensure a more equitable distribution of income and enhanced financial stability for individuals.

Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers (N=120)

The Table. 8 presented various constraints faced by farmers concerning the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY), a government crop insurance scheme in India as reported by 120 sampled insured farmers. The constraints were ranked based on their Garrette mean score and the corresponding percentage of impact as perceived by the farmers. This analysis helps identify the most critical challenges that hinder the effective implementation and adoption of the PMFBY scheme among farmers.

The results of Garrett's Ranking Technique reveal that the major constraints affecting the PMFBY include delay in payment of insurance claims (ranked I, 48.27%), insufficient compensation (ranked II, 45.88%), and ignorance about crops covered under the scheme (ranked III, 44.92%). Other notable constraints are lack of coordination between banks and farmers (ranked IV) and the negative

attitude of farmers (ranked V). Lower-ranked issues include inadequate transparency, lack of trustworthiness, and insufficient training programs, highlighting the need for improved claim processing, compensation, and awareness efforts to enhance the scheme's effectiveness.

Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY (N=120)

The suggestion given in Table 9 based on farmer responds, the frequency, proportion, and ranking of several proposals for enhancing the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY). In his remarks, the main conclusions from the data will be analysed, emphasizing how important and prioritized each recommendation is according to the respondents.

The most critical recommendation is to expedite the claims process, with 77.50% of respondents highlighting the need for timely compensation to support their financial stability. Expanding coverage for small farmers follows as a significant concern (71.67%), emphasizing the scheme's inclusiveness. The establishment of a dedicated PMFBY cell at the taluka level (66.67%) and increasing indemnity amounts (65.83%) also ranked highly, reflecting demands for better local support and adequate compensation for losses. While modernizing assessment methods with digital technology garnered interest, it was ranked lower (50.00%). Additionally, calls for greater transparency (60.00%) and a public grievance redressal mechanism (58.33%) underscore the need for accountability in the scheme. Overall, the findings highlight farmers' desire for an efficient, equitable, and transparent insurance system that adequately addresses their needs.

Conclusion

The performance of PMFBY in Parbhani district demonstrates steady growth in insurance participation and positive trends in insured area, approved claims, and farmer benefits, with a 4 per cent per annum CAGR for both Kharif and Rabi seasons. While Kharif reported claims and total claims paid showed significant growth of 13 per cent per annum and 15 per cent per annum, respectively, Rabi season indicators reflect challenges, including a -12 per cent per annum decline in benefits and a -9 per cent per annum drop in payouts. This highlights the need for addressing seasonal inconsistencies in support while maintaining the overall positive trajectory of the scheme in Parbhani, contrasting with the national decline in insured farmers.

The analysis indicates that compensation mechanisms significantly enhance income stability, as evidenced by lower variability and a higher average income in the "With Compensation" group compared to the "Without Compensation" group, along with improved consistency in income distribution.

The analysis identifies critical constraints in the implementation of the PMFBY, with the most significant challenges being delays in claims processing, insufficient compensation, and lack of awareness about covered crops, emphasizing the need for improved efficiency and communication to enhance the scheme's effectiveness among farmers. The analysis of farmer suggestions for improving the PMFBY emphasizes the need for a more efficient claims process, expanded coverage for small farmers, and enhanced local support, alongside greater transparency and accountability, to create a more equitable and effective insurance system.

References

1. **Aditya, K.S., Khan, M.T., and Kishore, A. (2018).** Adoption of crop insurance and impact: insights from India. *Agricultural Economics Research Review*. 31(2), 163-174.
2. **Bobade, A.H., & Mahajan, S.S. (2012).** Awareness of farmers about crop insurance schemes in Khatav taluka of Satara district. *International Research Journal of Agricultural Economics and Statistics*, 3(2), 75-80.
3. **Cariappa, A. G. A., Lokesh, G. B., Amrutha., Joshi, T., Reddy, B. S., & Hulagur, B. (2018).** Performance of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in Hyderabad-Karnataka (H-K) region. *J. Farm Sci.* 31(4), 452-456.

4. **Darshan Y. A., Ramakrishnan, K. A., Pushpa, J. A., & Prabakaran K. B. (2021).** Constraints and Suggestions Encountered by the Beneficiaries under Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana in Tumkur District of Karnataka. *AJAEES* .39(12),33-37.
5. **Devi, K., Gupta, S., & Devi, K. (2023).** Suggestions to overcome the constraints of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*. 12(5), 2268-2270.
6. **Goudappa, S. B., Reddy, B. S., & Chandrashekar, S. M. (2012).** Farmers perception and awareness about crop insurance in Karnataka. *Indian Research Journal of Extension Education*, 2, 218-222.
7. **Jiragal, I. M., Ganesamoorthi, S., Mohankumar, T. L., & Narayanswamy, C. (2023).** Constraints and Suggestions of Beneficiary and Non-beneficiary of Farmers towards Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana in Kolar District of Karnataka. *AJAEES* .41(4), 55-61.
8. **Kale, N. B., & Nagare, N. B. (2022).** Role of PMFBY in Agricultural Development in Marathwada Region. *Journal of Research & Development*. 14(20), 24-26.
9. **Mani, K., Chandrasekarana, M., & Selvanayaki, S. (2012).** Adaptability of Crop Insurance Schemes in Tamil Nadu. *Agricultural Economics Research Review*. 25(2), 279-290.
10. **Manisha, & Harpreet, K. (2019)** Performance of Crop Insurance Schemes in India -A Study of North-western States. *Journal of Agricultural Development and Policy*.29(1), 22-30.
11. **Mathur, A., & Gupta, S. (2019).** Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojna and Farm Risk Management: A study of Jammu District. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*. 6(1), 618-626.
12. **Mote, S.S., Sharma, A., Panda, S., & Rathore, R. (2017)** Impact of Crop Insurance on Farmers Income in Pune District of Maharashtra. *Indian Journal of Economics and Development*. 13(2), 617-622.
13. **Nagesh, H., Rao, B. M., & Krishna, T. G. (2022).** Constraints Faced by the Beneficiaries of PMFBY and Suggestions Given by Them to Overcome the Constraints in Srikakulam District of Andhra Pradesh. *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*. 41(35), 40-43.
14. **Nain, M. S., Rashmi Singh and Mishra, J. R., (2017)** A study of farmers 'awareness on agricultural insurance schemes in southern Haryana. *Indian Journal of Extension Education*, 53 (4): 75-79.
15. **Narwade, S.S., & Patwardhan, P. (2014)** District wise analysis of (NAIS) in Marathwada Region. *Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*. 1(2), 40-49.
16. **Rai, R. (2019)** Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana: An Assessment of India's Crop Insurance Scheme. *Observer Research Foundation. Issue Brief*. (296).
17. **Rathore, V.S., Burark, S.S. & Jain, H.K. (2011).** Performance of Crop Insurance Scheme in Udaipur District of Rajasthan. *Agricultural Economics Research Review*. 24, 5-35.
18. **Sharon, V. Kait, R. & Rani, M. (2023).** Assessing the Effectiveness of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana in Haryana. *IJESSM* .11(3), 350.
19. **Sporri, M., Baráth, L., Bokusheva, R and Ferto, I. 2012.** The impact of crop insurance on the economic performance of Hungarian cropping farms. Paper prepared for the 123rd European Association of Agricultural Economics (EAAE) Seminar. 1-15.
20. **Thangjam, D., Ozukum, L., & Feroze, S.M. (2018).** Crop insurance in Northeastern States of India: Performance of National Agricultural Insurance Scheme. *International Journal of Agriculture Sciences*. 10(11), 6325-6329.
21. **Varadan, R. J., & Kumar, P. (2012).** Impact of Crop Insurance on Rice Farming in Tamil Nadu. *Agricultural Economics Research Review*. 25(2), 291-298.

Table 1. Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of insured farmers under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl No.	Particular		Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-7**	-2**
		t value	-1.98	-0.62
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	20	3**
		t value	2.98	0.25
3	Parbhani	CAGR	4**	4**
		t value	2.95	0.23

Note: **Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 2. Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of area insured under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl No.	Particular		Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	1**	1**
		t value	0.51	0.34
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	19**	4**
		t value	1.34	0.29
3	Parbhani	CAGR	3**	4**
		t value	1.98	0.22

Note: **Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 3. Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of reported claims under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl No.	Particular		Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	8	44**
		t value	2.41	1.75
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-41**	1**

		t value	-1.52**	0.04
3	Parbhani	CAGR	1**	13**
		t value	0.08	0.27

Note: **Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 4. Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of approved claims under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl No.	Particular		Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-60**	-26**
		t value	-2.47	-.84
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-42**	3**
		t value	-1.57	0.11
3	Parbhani	CAGR	4**	5**
		t value	0.86	0.28

Note: **Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 5. Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of total claims paid under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23 (Kharif & Rabi).

Sl No.	Particular		Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-5**	-20**
		t value	-1.01	-2.35
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	7**	-13**
		t value	0.83	-0.55
3	Parbhani	CAGR	15**	-9**
		t value	1.25	-0.36

Note: **Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 6. Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of total farmers benefited under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23 (Kharif & Rabi).

Sl No.	Particular		Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-6**	-19**
		t value	-3.02	-2.41
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	1**	-19**
		t value	0.11	-0.73
3	Parbhani	CAGR	12**	-12**
		t value	1.29	-0.60

Note: **Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 7. Income stability and income index of sample insured farmers for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl. no.	Particular	Without compensation	With compensation
1	Standard deviation	14636.60	13722.80
2	Mean	67795.90	68352.20
3	COV	0.22	0.20
4	Income stability Index	0.78	0.80

Table 8: Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers by Garrett's ranking

Sl. No.	Constraints	Garrette mean score	Per cent (%)	Rank
1.	Inadequate transparency and accountability	49.76	34.56	VI
2.	Delay in payment of insurance claim	69.51	48.27	I
3.	Lack of coordination between banks and farmers	59.10	41.04	IV
4.	Ignorance about crops covered under the scheme	64.68	44.92	III
5.	insufficient training programme	33.34	23.15	VII
6.	Insufficient compensation under PMFBY	66.07	45.88	II
7.	Lack of trustworthiness	34.53	23.98	VIII
8.	Negative attitude of farmers toward this scheme	55.74	38.71	V
9.	Include coverage for post-harvest losses	32.84	22.81	IX
10.	Inadequate awareness about the scheme among farmers particularly small and marginal	27.67	19.22	X

Table 9. Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY

Sl. no	Suggestion	Frequency	Per cent	Rank
1	Creation of separate PMFBY cell at taluka level	80	66.67	III
2	Make the claim process faster for farmer, to receive timely compensation	93	77.50	I
3	Increase indemnity amount	79	65.83	IV
4	Increase coverage area to small farmers with landholding below a certain threshold	86	71.67	II
5	Use digital technology like drone, mobile app to assess crop damage	60	50.00	IX
6	Inform farmers before deducting premium	59	49.17	X
7	Provide uniform Indemnity for different regions and types of crops	67	55.83	VII
8	Providing assessment at the right time of crop loss	63	52.50	VIII
9	Establish public grievance settlement mechanism at local level	70	58.33	VI
10	Need for transparency in settlement of claim	72	60.00	V